

D7.2 Final EOSC Core Gap Analysis and Requirements Report

02/05/2025

Abstract

This is the final report of the requirement gathering and analysis process for enhancing the existing European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Core services, which are central to the EOSC Beyond project. The aim is to ensure these services meet the evolving needs of their stakeholders, encompassing end-users, service providers, and EOSC Nodes. Through rigorous engagement with various stakeholders and leveraging insights from previous EOSC initiatives, the document identifies existing gaps and proposes specific enhancements to align with the long-term objectives of the EOSC community.

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Executive Summary

This report presents the findings from the updated requirement gathering and analysis process for enhancing the Core services of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) as part of the EOSC Beyond project. Building on the previous deliverable (D7.1), this document focuses on new requirements identified since then, particularly those emerging from the two key workshops: the joint WP7 & WP8 Workshop held in Athens and the 2nd Pilot Nodes WP15 Workshop in Krakow.

The EOSC Federation will operate as a federated 'system of systems' made up of EOSC Nodes. A key gap identified in this architecture is the absence of a dedicated service for discovering and querying participating Nodes and their capabilities. Chapter 2 outlines the requirements for such a Node Registry service, based on discussions from the WP7&8 Workshop in Athens and further work by WP7.

Engagement with Pilot Nodes has revealed essential insights into the integrations among nodes, highlighting the necessity for support in enabling the composition of diverse resources originating from different nodes within the EOSC federation. This in-depth analysis has led to the identification of specific gaps that are critical for enhancing service functionality and ensuring seamless interoperability.

The report consolidates these newly recognized gaps into actionable requirements that will inform the ongoing requirements gathering and analysis process within EOSC Beyond. The requirements collected and analyzed from the Pilot Nodes are now broken down into detailed tasks and development tickets, which are actively progressing through the development phases in Work Package 8 (WP8).

As the EOSC Innovation Sandbox advances toward fostering a robust federation, the capabilities embedded within the EOSC Core must be designed for ease of deployment or offered as services. The findings emphasize the importance of an integrated EOSC Core platform that effectively addresses user requirements and enhances collaboration across diverse research environments.

In summary, this report outlines the updated requirements landscape and sets a direction for the continuous development of EOSC Core services, reinforcing the commitment to open science and facilitating enhanced cooperation among various research communities in Europe which are represented by the Pilot Nodes in the EOSC Beyond project.

1. Introduction

1.1. Scope and Purpose of the document

This final report presents the outcomes of Work Package 7 (WP7) in the EOSC Beyond project, which is dedicated to designing the next generation of EOSC Core services. The main objective of this report is to expand on the work initiated in Deliverable D7.1 by conducting a deeper analysis of the current Core services. The focus is on identifying opportunities for improvement to ensure that service evolution aligns with clearly identified needs and the enhancements outlined in the project's Description of Action (DoA).

Additionally, the report integrates insights and decisions from two key workshops: the joint WP7 & WP8 Workshop held in Athens and the Pilot Nodes WP15 Workshop in Krakow.

Ultimately, this document aims to perform a comprehensive gap analysis of the existing Core services based on the collected requirements. The findings will inform the specifications and designs that guide the forthcoming work in Work Packages 8 (WP8) and 9 (WP9). In this way, the report serves as a strategic framework to support the advancement of Core services within the EOSC Nodes Federation, promoting more effective integration and functionality tailored to stakeholder and user needs.

1.2. Structure of the document

This report is organised into five main sections, each serving a distinct purpose:

1. **Introduction:** This section.
2. **Requirements for a federation of autonomous Nodes:** presents the requirements that we came up with during the Workshop in Athens concerning building a federation of Nodes
3. **Requirements from the Pilot Nodes:** Requirements that are sourced from the Pilot nodes (Krakow Workshop) from the point of view of the Core Services.
4. **Gap Analysis and Requirement Capture for Each Core Service:** outlines the identified deficiencies, proposed enhancements, and user needs pertinent to enhancing their functionality and interoperability within the EOSC framework.
5. **Conclusions:** synthesises the insights presented in this report, reinforcing the importance of the findings in guiding the future development of the EOSC Core services in the scope of WP8 and WP9.

1.3. Definitions

The main definitions that are related to the EOSC Federation of Nodes used in this document are defined in the table below.

Definition	Description
EOSC User	Anyone who is granted access to the EOSC Federation resources based on the recognition of his/her identity by a service provider registered with the EOSC AAI system.
Resource	Services, catalogues, digital research objects (e.g. data, software), training resources, infrastructure and other assets that may be available in an EOSC Node and offered in the EOSC Federation.
Resource Provider	An organisation making a Resource available.
EOSC Resource Provider	An organisation making a Resource available to the EOSC Federation, whose resource is then called an "EOSC Federated Resource"
EOSC Node Architecture	A reference architecture that can be implemented by each Node of the federation for the operation of their services and resources
EOSC Node	An organisation complying with the EOSC Federation policies and legal framework, working at the local, national, regional, thematic or European level. An EOSC Node offers added value resources to the EOSC Federation and delivers federating capabilities in collaboration with other EOSC Nodes. Each EOSC Node has its autonomy, its own governance model and an offer in terms of resources. It operates its own platform, complying with the technical framework, and the EOSC Federation Platform architecture.
EOSC Node Host	The legal entity representing an EOSC Node, and entering into the EOSC Collaboration Agreement.
EOSC Federated Resources	The set of all resources that EOSC Nodes share with the EOSC Federation (such a set was previously called "EOSC Exchange")
EOSC Interoperability Framework (IF)	An extensible framework of guidelines that acts as the glue to support the interoperability and composability of EOSC Federated resources. The EOSC IF is a reference framework to promote standards and best practices, but offers the freedom to providers to develop and operate provider-specific implementations while conforming to the EOSC IF guidelines and standards
EOSC Federation	The network of EOSC Nodes
EOSC Tripartite Governance:	The strategic coordination between the EU (represented by the EC), the Member States and Associated Countries represented by the EC Expert Group ('EOSC-Steering Board'), and the EOSC Association (represented by EOSC-A Board).

EOSC Tripartite Group:	The group appointed representatives of the three parties of the EOSC Tripartite Governance.
Onboarding Resources in an EOSC Node:	Onboarding a resource in an EOSC Node means. Making available this resource to the users through that Node. A provider selects the most appropriate Nodes (it can be more than one) based on the characteristics of the resource. For example, if a provider has a domain-specific data repository, it may choose a thematic node that best represents and serves that domain
Enrolling an EOSC Node:	For the EOSC Federation to enroll a node means to register and integrate it in the EOSC Federation. Once a node has been enrolled, a new entry for the Node is created in the Eosc Node Registry and the Node can share its resources and federating capabilities, which can include resources provided by the node itself or by resource providers onboarded on the EOSC Node.
EOSC Thematic Node:	Communities that are working in a specific scientific domain of research or with specific techniques. A technique can cover a large number of scientific domains, e.g. photon sources.
EOSC National/Regional Nodes	An EOSC Node for a regional or national community
EOSC Federating Capabilities	EOSC Federating Capabilities are the added-value capabilities offered by the EOSC Federation that allow all EOSC end-users and providers to exploit services, data and other resources in the Federation.
Node Core functions	The Node Core functions enable the basic operation of an EOSC Node. An initial reference implementation of these Node Core functions has been implemented by the EOSC EU Node. The Node Core functions can be implemented by an EOSC Node as functions of a platform, individual services, or acquired through the EOSC Federation (offered as-a-Service or using the technology of the reference implementation).
Node Generic functions:	Employed in the vast majority of scientific disciplines (and therefore relevant to all EOSC Nodes) to perform everyday tasks related to research data management.
Node Resources	Services, data and other research products, usually listed in a catalogue, that end-users of this Node can access directly.
Node Exchange:	Services and other resources a Node shares with the EOSC Federation. They contribute to the collective EOSC Exchange.
Other services and resources	Resources accessible via a Node but not shared with the Federation.

Table 1: Definitions

1.4. Federation Capabilities

According to the EOSC handbook, the initial federating capabilities are as listed below.

Federating Capability	Description	Classification
Resource Catalogues and Registry Services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Federated EOSC Resource Catalogue (services, datasets and other research products) • Advanced search engine • Interfaces to allow EOSC Nodes to publish (push) and retrieve (pull) resources to/from the federated catalogue 	Mandatory
AAI	Allows users to log in with their own institute credentials (eduGAIN) to access EOSC resources	Mandatory
Application Workflow Management	Orchestrate services, datasets and other research objects on multiple federated nodes	Mandatory
Service Monitoring	Provide information about the availability and quality of EOSC services (Core and Exchange)	Mandatory
Service and Research Product Accounting	Provide information about usage of services and resources in EOSC (Core and Exchange)	Mandatory
Order Management	Offer a framework for providers to define offers and a unique interface for end-users to request access to resources	Mandatory
Helpdesk	Federation of integrated helpdesks	Mandatory
Management System	FitSM-based Service Management System (SMS) that can be federated with SMS from other EOSC Nodes. This includes Security Coordination between Nodes too.	Recommended

Table 2 - Initial federating capabilities

2. Requirements for a Federation of Nodes

According to the architecture outlined in the EOSC Federation Handbook, the EOSC Federation is designed to equip Europe's research community with the digital tools and resources necessary to carry out research across disciplines and borders, in alignment with FAIR data principles and open science, within a secure and trustworthy environment driven by scientific communities. This vision is realized through the establishment of a 'system of systems'—a federated network of institutional, regional, national, and European data repositories, research infrastructures, e-infrastructure, and other scientific service providers, collectively organized as EOSC Nodes. Each EOSC Node may consist of a single organization or a consortium, with its own internal governance, contributing services and resources to the wider Federation. These Nodes must be represented by a legal entity and are required to comply with the Federation's policies, rules, and decisions. A key identified

gap in this architecture is the lack of a dedicated service that enables the identification, search, listing, and querying of Nodes participating in the Federation, along with their respective federating capabilities. In this chapter, we outline the requirements of a Node Registry service as they were discussed in the WP7&8 Workshop in Athens and were further defined by WP7.

Figure 1: Requirements of a Node Registry service

2.1. Objectives

The objectives of the Node Registry System are to:

- Develop a secure and scalable registry for managing node metadata
- Enable efficient node discovery and retrieval
- Implement an API for seamless integration with external services
- Ensure all API responses are machine-actionable
- Allow each node to expose its federating capabilities
- Be scalable and distributed so as to be resilient
- Be governance agnostic

2.2. Features

The main features of the Node Registry System are:

- **Node Registration:** Allow nodes to register with unique identifiers (PIDs) and metadata.
- **Node Discovery:** Enable querying and retrieving registered nodes based on criteria.
- **Authentication & Authorisation:** Ensure only verified nodes can access or modify the registry.
- **API Interface:** Provides RESTful endpoints for integration.

2.3. EOSC Beyond Design of the EOSC Node Registry Architecture

The proposed architecture consists of the following:

- **EOSC Node Registry (ENR)** a service that acts as the registration authority for EOSC Nodes metadata, including PID as obtained by the EOSC PID Service. It also operates as an aggregator of metadata about capabilities from EOSC Nodes. It exposes a Rest API.
- **EOSC Node Endpoint (ENE)** service running on an EOSC Node and listing Node capabilities and corresponding metadata. It exposes a Rest API for querying by the Node Client.
- **EOSC Node Client (ENC)** enabling the communication between the components.

The architecture reflects the federative flavour of the EOSC in that it defines:

- An EOSC Node Registry (ENR) that addresses the need to identify and describe properties of EOSC Nodes;
- Foresees EOSC Nodes as entities that independently expose their capabilities' metadata via ENEs (APIs) to any interested party;
- Enables a scenario where the EOSC Node Registry interacts with Nodes and collects metadata capabilities from their ENEs to enable cross-node discovery of capabilities.

As we shall see in the next section, an implementation can follow a two-stage process, where first the EOSC Node Registry is delivered (MvP) and, in the second stage, the Registry is equipped with cross-node discovery capabilities by interacting with EOSC Nodes implementing ENEs.

2.3.1. Registration: Sample Node Entry in the Registry

Sample of a node entry:

- Name:
- Logo:
- Description

- PID: (auto-generated by the system)
- Website:
- Legal Entity: Name, Acronym, and ROR ID
- Contact persons:
 - Names and emails (and ORCID IDs) for the roles identified by the EC during the candidate node selection: Coordinator, Technical Manager, Operational Manager, Security Manager, Federation and Scientific Officer, Training Officer
- ENE (Node endpoint): API that returns metadata describing capabilities of the node

2.3.2. Example of the Node Registry API Response in JSON Format

```
{
  {
    "id" : XXX
    "name": "Example EOSC Node",
    "logo": "https://example.com/logo.png",
    "pid": "hdl:20.500.12345/abcde",
    "legal_entity": {
      "name": "Example Research Organization",
      "ror_id": "https://ror.org/012345678"
    },
    "node_endpoint": "https://example.com/api/node",
    "capabilities": ["Monitoring", "Accounting",...]
  }
}
```

2.3.3. Example of the Node Endpoint API Response in JSON Format

```
{
  "node_endpoint": "https://example.com/api/node",
  "capabilities": [
    {
      "capability_type": "Resource Catalogue",
      "endpoint": "https://example.com/api/resource-catalogue",
      "version": "3.0"
    },
    {
      "capability_type": "Identity Management",
      "endpoint": "https://example.com/api/identity-management",
      "version": "2.1"
    },
    {
```

```

    "capability_type": "Application Workflow Management",
    "endpoint": "https://example.com/api/workflow-management",
    "version": "1.5"
  },
  {
    "capability_type": "Service Monitoring",
    "endpoint": "https://example.com/api/service-monitoring",
    "version": "1.2"
  },
  {
    "capability_type": "Service Accounting",
    "endpoint": "https://example.com/api/service-accounting",
    "version": "1.0"
  },
  {
    "capability_type": "Order Management",
    "endpoint": "https://example.com/api/order-management",
    "version": "2.0"
  },
  {
    "capability_type": "Management System (including
Helpdesk)",
    "endpoint": "https://example.com/api/management-system",
    "version": "1.3"
  }
}

```

2.4. Requirements for all Core Services

According to the proposed architecture, each Core Service within the EOSC Federation should be enhanced to explicitly expose its capabilities in a common and interoperable manner. This will ensure that services can seamlessly interact and integrate with equivalent or complementary services offered by other EOSC Nodes. Such interoperability is essential for fostering cross-node collaboration, enabling unified service composition, and supporting the broader vision of a cohesive, federated ecosystem. By making capabilities discoverable and accessible, Core Services can contribute more effectively to the overall functionality and scalability of the Federation.

3. Requirements from the Pilot Nodes

This section presents the requirements identified through direct engagement with the Pilot Nodes involved in the EOSC Beyond project. These requirements are critical for informing the development and enhancement of the EOSC Core services, particularly in the context of establishing a functional and interoperable federation of EOSC Nodes. While initial requirements from the Pilot Nodes were explored in D15.1 and integrated into the analysis in D7.1, this section focuses on the second workshop, which provided a deeper, more structured input from the participating pilots.

The aim of this activity was to gather detailed functional and technical requirements emerging from the user stories and integration scenarios proposed by the Pilot Nodes. These requirements reflect the current capabilities and expectations of Node operators and are instrumental in defining a realistic roadmap for the EOSC Core evolution.

3.1. Methodology and inputs gathered

The second workshop represented a follow-up phase in the planning of the integrations. The first workshop is documented in Deliverable 15.1, and its outcomes were taken into account in Deliverable 7.1. This section focuses on the second workshop, during which the pilot teams, across several sessions, were asked to provide input.

During the workshop, participants were asked to contribute structured information based on their specific implementation plans and service integration needs within the EOSC Federation. The methodology adopted for collecting these requirements included a combination of guided discussions, template-based requirement capture, and collaborative analysis across use cases. The key inputs gathered from the Pilot Nodes included:

- **Exchange Services to Offer:** A list of the services that each Pilot Node intends to provide as part of the EOSC Exchange, with emphasis on services that will be made accessible to other Nodes and the broader EOSC ecosystem.
- **User Stories and Use Case Analysis:** Each Pilot presented detailed user stories representing their target communities and identified the workflows they plan to support within the EOSC Federation.
- **Inter-Pilot Connections:** Identification of potential collaborations and service integration scenarios between Pilot Nodes, highlighting use cases that cross national or institutional boundaries.
- **Technical Integration Requirements:** Technical assessments were carried out to identify integration points and needs for EOSC Core services, especially in terms of AAI, service catalogues, helpdesk, monitoring, and accounting.
- **Core Services Requirements:** Concrete technical and functional requirements targeting the enhancement or adaptation of EOSC Core services to better support the needs of the Pilots.
- **Implementation Roadmaps:** A high-level roadmap from each Pilot Node outlining their timeline, priorities, and anticipated milestones for integrating into the EOSC Federation.

These findings represent the consolidated perspective of the Pilot Nodes and directly inform the gap analysis and prioritization process described in Section 4. The full breakdown of inputs, including Pilot-by-Pilot summaries and requirement tables, is provided in **Appendix 1**.

3.2. Main conclusions from the Pilot Nodes user stories analysis

A cross-analysis of the user stories and service plans revealed several recurring themes and common challenges across the Pilot Nodes:

1. **Demand for Stronger Service Interoperability:** Many pilots require seamless integration of services across Nodes, pointing to the need for enhanced interoperability support at the Core level, including standard APIs and shared resource identifiers.
2. **Federated Identity and Access Requirements:** Pilots emphasized the importance of a robust, scalable, and user-friendly AAI that can support both institutional and community identities, with federated access to resources across Nodes.
3. **Service Discoverability and Monitoring:** The user stories revealed the need for improved discoverability of services and providers via the EOSC Marketplace, as well as real-time integration with monitoring tools to enable reliable operations and reporting.
4. **Support for Usage Reporting and Impact Assessment:** Several pilots indicated the necessity for fine-grained accounting and reporting capabilities, particularly for demonstrating impact and usage to funders and stakeholders.
5. **Operational Integration with Helpdesk and Support Tools:** Many use cases highlight the need for Helpdesk-as-a-Service to be fully embedded into the user workflows, including integration with the provider and user dashboards.

Taking into account the services discussed during the integration analysis and the requirements necessary for their implementation, the general conclusions regarding the core services are as follows:

- The Marketplace and Discovery Hub must provide a federated discovery environment that supports the integration of multiple catalogues, including thematic, national, and institutional sources. It should enable users to independently discover and access services and datasets across the EOSC network. This includes support for harmonised metadata ingestion, cross-node search capabilities, and a self-service interface to browse, request, or launch services. The system should allow ingestion of metadata feeds via standardised protocols and offer sufficient flexibility to accommodate varied catalogue structures.
- A service ordering framework must support structured request handling for all types of EOSC services, including computing, data access, and instrument booking. Users must be able to submit, track, and manage service requests, with visibility into service status, delivery timelines, and SLAs. The order management system should support feedback and coordination mechanisms between service providers and requesters and be interoperable with other relevant services (AAI, Monitoring, etc.).
- A federated helpdesk should provide integration between local helpdesks and a central support layer, allowing users to access a single entry point for assistance.

The system must support thematic routing, traceable workflows, and integration with service catalogues and SLAs. Clear onboarding processes, documentation, and interoperability standards are necessary to ensure a consistent user experience regardless of the underlying support structure.

- Monitoring capabilities must enable real-time and historical visibility of service health, availability, and usage across the EOSC federation. This includes support for domain-specific monitoring probes and common interfaces for exposing performance data. The monitoring framework must be adjustable enough to support infrastructure-level and service-level metrics, and extensible to cover distributed services, including HPC and cloud-based resources. Guidance and tooling are needed to ensure that all nodes can contribute to a federated monitoring view.
- The Service Catalogue should provide a structured and flexible registry for all EOSC-integrated services. It must support the distinction between local, national, and federated services and enable communities to curate service visibility for their users. The catalogue should also act as a backend to the Discovery Hub, supporting tagging, classification, and integration with other core services such as Helpdesk, Monitoring, and Order Management. Interoperability with external catalogues and metadata harmonisation are also key requirements.
- The Resource Catalogue must serve as a federated registry for research products, and other scientific outputs. To ensure proper discoverability, the catalogue must support metadata interoperability across institutional, national, and thematic repositories, PIDs, and standard schemas that enable machine-readable relationships between resources. A key requirement is the ability to federate metadata from existing community catalogues while maintaining consistency and FAIR principles.
- Federated AAI mechanisms must support identity integration across institutional and community identity providers. It should allow for role-based and group-based access control, enabling collaborative workflows across infrastructures. Harmonisation of group membership and role information is essential to ensure secure, collaboration-based user access to distributed EOSC services and data.
- The Deployment Service must provide automated, policy-compliant provisioning of infrastructure services such as compute and storage. It should support deployments triggered from the Service Catalogue or Marketplace/Discovery Hub, and enable the co-deployment of research data or products alongside services. Federation-aware orchestration is needed to handle deployments across distributed infrastructures with differing resource allocation models. The system must also include mechanisms for integrating user credentials, monitoring hooks, and resource quotas.
- A PID infrastructure must support automated PID assignment, resolution, and linkage across EOSC services. The system should integrate with data repositories, research product catalogues, and publication workflows to ensure findability, traceability, and long-term data reference. The PID service must be able to function across disciplines and infrastructures, and offer APIs or tools for integration into service workflows and catalogue registration processes.

These findings represent the consolidated perspective of the Pilot Nodes and directly inform the gap analysis and prioritization process described in Section 4. The full breakdown of inputs, including Pilot-by-Pilot summaries and requirement tables, is provided in Appendix 1.

4. Gap Analysis and Requirement Capture for Each Core Component.

This section of the report presents the updated requirements analysis for each individual capability within the EOSC Core, building upon the work previously documented in D7.1.

4.1. AAI

4.1.1 Summary of gaps identified in D7.1

- GAP: Inconsistent handling of advanced authentication mechanisms (ID: WP7-R68, Requestor: D5.1)

Requirement: Support Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA) Across EOSC Nodes

The AAI inconsistently handles advanced authentication methods like Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA). The AAI must prioritise the MFA capabilities of the user's home Identity Provider (IdP), provide fallback mechanisms when the home IdP lacks support, and ensure interoperability across EOSC Nodes using protocols like OpenID Connect and SAML2.

- GAP: EOSC federated AAI lacks native support for OpenID Connect (ID: WP7-R69, Requestor: D5.1)

Requirement: Support for OpenID Connect Federations

AAI services should support [OpenID Federation](#) to enable dynamic trust establishment for OpenID Connect and OAuth 2.0 flows, allowing EOSC Nodes to securely interact without requiring manual trust agreements.

- GAP: Lack of Harmonised Approach to Authorisation (ID: WP7-R70, Requestor: D5.1)

Requirement: Support for Advanced Authorisation Mechanisms

The fragmented state of authorisation across research infrastructures hinders consistent policy enforcement and resource sharing. To address this, the AAI must provide advanced, harmonised authorisation support mechanisms that enable EOSC Nodes to handle user and resource information consistently across infrastructures, ensuring interoperability and uniform policy enforcement using common standards defined in the AARC Blueprint Architecture.

- GAP: AAI Interoperability with SIMPL (ID: WP7-R71, Requestor: D5.1)

Requirement: Integration Analysis of SIMPL IAA Framework with EOSC Federated AAI

SIMPL-based data spaces use diverse identification, authentication, and authorisation mechanisms, including decentralised identity models. A study is needed to evaluate SIMPL's Identification, Authentication, and Authorisation (IAA) framework and identify interoperability pathways with the EOSC Federated AAI.

- GAP: Lack of Standardised User and Access Provisioning (ID: WP7-R72, Requestor: D5.1)

Requirement: Proof of Concept for User and Access Provisioning

The AAI needs a standardised approach to user and access provisioning and deprovisioning. To address this, the goal is to implement and demonstrate standards-based mechanisms, such as SCIM, to ensure secure and efficient user and access management across services.

4.1.2 Post-D7.1 Analysis

The following gaps/requirements have been refined:

- **ID: WP7-R68, Requirement: MFA Support Across EOSC Nodes**

This requirement ensures consistent Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA) support across EOSC Nodes, enabling dynamic MFA requests and fallback options when home Identity Providers (IdPs) lack MFA support.

Refinements:

- Aligned MFA signalling with the [REFEDS MFA Profile](#) for OpenID Connect (OIDC) and SAML.
- Prioritised home IdP MFA with the Node AAI fallback using, for example, One-Time Passwords (OTPs).
- Emphasised OIDC-based MFA signalling for node-to-node AAI interactions.

Objectives and Acceptance Criteria:

- MFA signalling complies with the [REFEDS MFA Profile](#) when interacting with home IdPs using either OIDC or SAML.
 - MFA signalling for node-to-node AAI interactions uses OIDC and adheres to the [REFEDS MFA Profile](#).
 - Services can dynamically or statically request MFA via OIDC, prioritising home IdP MFA.
 - The Node AAI may provide OTP-based fallback when home IdP lacks MFA
- **ID: WP7-R69, Requirement: Support for OpenID Federation**

This requirement enables native OpenID Connect (OIDC) and OAuth 2.0 flows in the EOSC Federated AAI by implementing [OpenID Federation](#), automating trust establishment across EOSC Nodes.

Refinements:

- Adopted Federation Entity metadata per [OpenID Federation](#) to model member metadata.
- Adopted Trust Anchors and Trust Mark Issuers per [OpenID Federation](#) to support the trust infrastructure.

Objectives and Acceptance Criteria:

- Node AAI services support [OpenID Federation](#) for dynamic trust establishment (without manual trust agreements).
 - Trust infrastructure complies with the [OpenID Federation](#) specification, including Trust Anchors and Trust Marks.
 - Secure interactions between EOSC Nodes are based on native OIDC and OAuth 2.0 flows.
- **ID: WP7-R72, Requirement: Proof of Concept for User and Access Provisioning**

This requirement standardises user and access provisioning/deprovisioning across a Node's services using standards like SCIM.

Refinements:

- Prioritised for WP9 to address use cases where core services require standards-based APIs for group and role management.
- Focused on SCIM for consistent and interoperable provisioning/deprovisioning workflows.

Objectives and Acceptance Criteria:

- Proof of concept demonstrates SCIM-based provisioning/deprovisioning across services within a Node.
- Standards-based API supports managing group membership and roles.

4.2. Accounting for research products

No new requirements have arisen, so the roadmap and tasks for the Accounting for research products Service remain unchanged regarding the plans presented in D7.1.

4.3. Accounting for services

This section presents an update to the gap analysis originally outlined in D7.1 for Accounting for services. While many of the requirements are still being developed, most of those identified in D7.1 remain relevant. The following updates and additions have been made to the existing requirements.

GAP: National or Thematic Node integration

The revised architecture indicates that the Accounting Service implements the following requirements.

- A generic entity that serves as the root of the hierarchical accounting structure. This entity can be designated by the client as either a Node (i.e., National, or Thematic) or a dedicated Project. Depending on the selected designation, the appropriate attributes and configurations will be associated with the entity, allowing for adaptable integration and customized functionality to accommodate different organizational models, thematic frameworks, or individual Projects.
- New REST API endpoints, as well as enhancements to existing ones, will be required to support the creation, association, and management of the respective root entities.

GAP: Report generation per Project, Provider, Resource, National or Thematic Node

To achieve the desired outcomes, the following requirements need to be fulfilled.

- Support an aggregation function for report purposes, therefore, the system must be capable of handling records with overlapping time ranges, necessitating the development of a specialized algorithm to correctly process and consolidate such data.

GAP: Enhancing EOSC Profiles with Service Accounting Data: Integrating the Resource Catalogue

Concerning the integration with the Service Catalogue, the following requirements have been raised.

- Each node's Service Catalogue instance should correspond to a dedicated Node in the Accounting Service and have the ability to execute operations on it.
- The Service Catalogue's operations in the Accounting Service should be confronted with a coherency mechanism to ensure that the creation or modification of Providers and Services is accurately propagated to the Accounting Service.
- The Provider's representative should be able to be acknowledged with the hierarchical structure created in the Accounting Service.

4.4. Helpdesk

This section provides an update on the gap analysis initially presented in D7.1 for the Helpdesk. Several requirements have been successfully implemented in the EOSC beyond Helpdesk currently available in the sandbox.

Most of the requirements described in D7.1 remain valid. The following updates and additions have been identified on the existing requirements:

- **WP7-R125 Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Improve integration with EOSC Core components (Service Provider Dashboard for providers-EPOT team interaction, Marketplace for users-EOSC support group interactions).**

This requirement will be enhanced by adding multiple webforms to facilitate interaction between EOSC Core components and the Helpdesk. In addition, the user experience for order management will be enhanced by integration between Marketplace and Helpdesk. The onboarding process and communication between service providers and the onboarding team will be streamlined by enabling ticket creation from Service Provider Dashboard.

- **ID:WP7-R110 Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Delivery of Enhanced Helpdesk-as-a-Service**

In addition to the features listed in D7.1, a new functionality has been introduced allowing notification emails to be configured for each domain through the admin interface.

- **ID: WP7-R120 Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Pilot integration with NFDI HIFIS Zammad instance based on the new prototype**

The above mentioned requirement has changed to:

New Requirement: **Pilot integration with NFDI Helpdesk test instance**

In addition, three new requirements have been identified:

- Integration of EOSC Beyond Helpdesk with **CESSDA Helpdesk**, applying bi-directional synchronization.
- Integration of EOSC Beyond Helpdesk with **METROFOOD Helpdesk**, applying bi-directional synchronization.
- Integration of EOSC Beyond Helpdesk with **EGI Helpdesk**, applying bi-directional synchronization.

4.5. Interoperability Framework Registry

Summary of gaps/requirements already identified and described in D7.1:

- **Interoperability Registry needs to support machine-readable guidelines** (ID: WP7-R47, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Extend IF Guidelines to comply with TOSCA. Link with Services Adapters)

This requirement has two main aspects:

- EOSC IF Registry should support machine-readable specifications for the composability of resources
- Service Providers should have the ability to offer optional (in terms of service definition) software tools in the form of 'adapters' to facilitate the integration of external tools to their services *that are optionally related to IF Guidelines*.

After post D7.1 analysis, this requirement has been further extended by:

- Specifications on how IG Configuration Templates are created on the Interoperability Registry side, and how Service Providers are going to use them to create instances for their own services. Configuration Template schemas are to be created for each Guideline based on a specific formalization (which at the beginning could be a simple list of key-value pairs; this can be later improved to support complex schemas). Also, Providers portal will be updated to support editing of Configuration Template instances using a specialized schema-agnostic editor.
- The definition of procedures for onboarding adapters: adapters are to be onboarded as a separate type of resource in the Service Catalogue, and they are to be linked optionally with IF Guidelines stored in the registry. IF Registry should support this Adapter-Guideline link. Also, specifications of curation of adapters have been generated to specify how Service Providers and third-party Adapter authors will onboard their adapters.

For all the above, Tasks and Subtasks have been created in the Technical Roadmap Jira instance.

4.6. Marketplace - Research Service Gateway as a part of Front Office

This section provides an update on the progress made since Deliverable D7.1, according to the distinction of the EOSC Marketplace. Key achievements include initiating the separation of the discovery functionality from the Marketplace user interface, designing enhanced search criteria, preliminary integration steps with the EOSC Execution Framework, and developing a concept for a Federated Service Catalogue. All these activities aim to improve the value and usability of the Marketplace for end users and service providers.

Gap: Distinction of Marketplace – new understanding of the user-facing core services

Current State: We have recently started the concept phase for a new approach to the Marketplace. The idea is to turn it into a standalone product that can be offered on its own to different Infrastructures and Nodes. The new concept of the Marketplace is being designed for environments where operations are clearly defined and where there is a need for better tools to support service discovery and access.

At the same time, the concept of the Marketplace as a **system supporting federated discovery, access and re-use** is being developed.

As a result, we are offering a unified **Front Office** – a family of solutions exposing functionalities for users in the federated infrastructure, supporting discovery, access, and reuse of scientific resources.

This concept serves as an umbrella term to communicate a coherent structure of multiple interconnected services that form the user-facing layer of the system. By presenting the Front Office as a cohesive suite rather than separate units, we simplify both the management and the perception of the platform, while accurately reflecting its technical architecture.

The most adapted solution for multiple deployments in a federated environment is a new version of the EOSC Marketplace: Research Service Gateway supporting service discovery, access and re-use.

Resource Discovery Hub and ReSearch Connect are solutions focused on implementing new EOSC federating capabilities: federated discovery of resources, federated access and re-use of resources, federated user spaces and **are included in the EOSC Beyond's Innovation Sandbox** as a reference implementation of the new federating capabilities.

1. Research Service Gateway

Core EOSC Service: Enabling federated service discovery, access and re-use

Formerly known as the Marketplace, Research Service Gateway is a core service proposition for EOSC Nodes, implementing federated service discovery, access, and re-use. Designed for communities unified at both operational and technical levels, it serves as the central entry point for accessing services, analytical tools, data management solutions, storage, and computing resources essential for research. This integrated service simplifies access to a broad range of services across various research domains, offering not only data but also comprehensive data analytics tools from local, national, and international providers, including major European e-Infrastructures and Research Infrastructures.

2. Resource Discovery Hub

Core EOSC Service: Enabling federated resource discovery

Resource Discovery Hub is a new core service within the EOSC federation, implementing joint discovery and access to all EOSC resources. It allows users to browse and search through the complete offering of EOSC Exchange resources, such as publications, datasets, software, services, data sources, and more. Functioning primarily as an advanced search facility with an intuitive user interface, it displays each resource's metadata, allowing users to easily assess the relevance and potential value of each resource before requesting access. This hub is accessible to both authenticated and unauthenticated users.

3. ReSearchConnect

Core EOSC Service: Enabling federated user workspace and collaboration, resource access and re-use

Formerly known as the User Dashboard, a core service which has evolved and expanded with a range of new features, all designed to support users throughout their academic journey. Initially, it was simply a "dashboard": a semi-personalised space where researchers could receive resource recommendations, add items to their favourites, or keep up with the latest news from the world of science.

However, with the opportunities enabled by federation, a new version of the service was designed, rebranded, and introduced as ReSearchConnect.

ReSearchConnect represents the federated user space capability within EOSC. Its main goal is to enable the composition and execution of diverse resources offered by different nodes across the federation. ReSearchConnect provides a collaborative research environment focusing on the perspective of the user and offering to them access and re-use of the resources tailored to their needs and characteristics.

Key Benefits

1. **Improved User Experience**

The front office design makes it easier for users to discover resources and access service offers through a clear and user-friendly interface.

2. **Flexible Integration with Infrastructures**

As a standalone product, the Marketplace can be easily adapted to different infrastructures with specific operational needs.

3. **Better Support for Federated Research**

The modular structure (Discovery Hub, Access Gate, etc.) supports collaboration and access across diverse, decentralised systems.

Next Steps: Continued development of concepts will involve further prototyping, integration testing, and gradual rollout to ensure a smooth transition to the new approach. Starting with this deliverable, new naming will be used.

ID: WP7-R131, **Requestor:** Product Team, **Requirement:** Refactoring user interfaces for improved readability and intuitive navigation.

Summary of remaining gaps:

The following gaps remain relevant and will be addressed in the upcoming phases:

- **EOSC Marketplace for Service Discovery by IF Guidelines, Programming Language, or Platform:**
 - Current discovery functions lack specific filters for IF Guidelines, programming languages, and platforms.
 - Future phases will introduce these specific filters and improve metadata significantly for resource discoverability and integration capabilities.
 - **ID:** WP7-R53, WP7-R54, WP7-R55, WP7-R64, WP7-R66, **Requestor:** D5.1.
- **Execution of e-infra services from a common User Space:**
 - Currently, e-infra services are individually managed, limiting the user experience.
 - Upcoming activities aim at enabling unified execution of e-infra services at the EOSC federation level, integrating user journeys with the EOSC Deployment Service and Order Management System.
 - **ID:** WP7-R132, **Requestor:** Product Team.
- **Federated Catalogue implementation:**
 - Currently, EOSC relies on a centralised discovery model.
 - Moving towards a federated catalogue remains essential to provide localised access to federated resources, supporting modular and flexible discovery.
 - Initial implementations are underway, with ongoing refinements planned due to the complexity of full-scale federated integration.
 - **ID:** WP7-R133, **Requestor:** Product Team.

4.7. Messaging Service

No new requirements have arisen, so the roadmap and tasks for the Messaging Service remain unchanged regarding the plans presented in D7.1.

4.8. Monitoring Service

This section presents an update to the gap analysis originally outlined in D7.1 for Service Monitoring. While many of the requirements are still being developed, most of those identified in D7.1 remain relevant. The following updates and additions have been made to the existing requirements.

GAP: Monitoring as a service (MaaS)

Enable the definition of new monitoring metrics by the providers (WP7-R84)

The process of deployment of new monitoring metrics unfortunately can not be fully automated, due to the fact that all new probes and metrics need to be tested, and possibly

changed during the testing phase. Therefore, we can strive to make this process as automated as possible.

At the moment, we can submit a monitoring metric candidate using POEM. POEM is the component of the monitoring service used for the management of resources needed for successful monitoring (probes, metrics, profiles). The Monitoring team is notified when the new candidate is submitted, and admins can create new probes and metrics after the submitted candidate has been reviewed and properly tested.

The submitter needs to provide the basic information needed in order to set it up: the name of the probe, its description, link to the documentation, link to the probe itself, and contact information of the submitter. The probe can be sent either as an .rpm package, or as a script. The submitter should also provide a command with which the probe should be invoked.

It is necessary to provide the proper contact, so that the Monitoring team can contact the submitter. In the testing phase, we need to remove all the possible problems with the probe. Also, the Monitoring team will inform the submitter when the probe is ready to be deployed in the (pre-)production environment. It should also be mentioned here that the probes must adhere to the [guidelines for monitoring probes](#).

This process should be further improved, by creating the web form through which the probes may be more easily submitted for review and testing.

See: <https://jira.eqi.eu/browse/EBTR-48>

GAP: Tighter integration with Service Registry and Profiles is required in order to improve insights of the services available, including performance metrics.

Monitoring of service performance (WP7-R93)

The Monitoring Service shall extend its current functionality, which focuses on service status monitoring through a defined set of probes and metrics, to also support the collection, storage, and visualization of service performance data. This includes, but is not limited to, metrics such as website response times and other relevant performance parameters.

To enable this, the following capabilities must be ensured:

- Monitoring probes shall support the inclusion of performance data alongside service status, following the provided implementation guidelines and data format specifications.
- Probe developers shall be able to attach an arbitrary number of performance metrics to each status report.
- The monitoring engine shall incorporate a time-series database (e.g., TimescaleDB) optimized for the efficient storage and retrieval of performance data per monitored endpoint.

- The user interface shall provide a dedicated view for plotting and displaying performance metrics for each monitored service, enabling users to track trends and analyze system behavior over time.

These enhancements aim to provide a more comprehensive monitoring framework, allowing for deeper insights into both the health and performance of services.

See: <https://jira.egi.eu/browse/EBTR-57>

Extend the Monitoring Integration Profiles with service properties (WP7-R82)

Currently, the monitoring service relies on the Resource Catalogue (service registry) as its primary source of topology information. While this integration provides a foundational overview of service components, there is significant potential to enhance its capabilities. By extending the existing integration with additional metadata fields – such as detailed service descriptions, functional classifications, operational status indicators, and usage context – the monitoring service could deliver greater business value.

These enhancements would not only enrich the contextual understanding of each service but also enable more nuanced analysis, such as identifying usage patterns, performance trends, and areas for optimization. With more comprehensive and descriptive data, the system could provide deeper insights into service behavior and health, support better-informed decision-making, and facilitate proactive management. Ultimately, this would contribute to a more intelligent and adaptive monitoring framework that evolves alongside the services it observes.

See: <https://jira.egi.eu/browse/EBTR-46>

4.9. Order Management

Current State: Compared to Deliverable D7.1, previously identified gaps related to the EOSC Order Management Service remain relevant. Significant progress has been made regarding consumable resources: a basic design is complete, and soon a simple consumption counter for offers will be introduced, allowing providers to track resource consumption directly.

Additionally, a new GAP has emerged concerning the ordering system's back office capabilities. Currently, the ordering system is handled through JIRA, which has proven to be costly, inflexible, difficult to customise effectively, and limited in providing a user-friendly ordering experience. Therefore, a dedicated Backoffice Ordering System is under consideration to overcome these limitations.

Next Steps: Continued efforts will focus on finalising the consumable resource counter implementation, integrating service accounting solutions, and conducting feasibility studies for developing a dedicated back office ordering system.

IDs: WP7-R15, WP7-R134, **Requestor:** DoA, Product Team.

4.10. PID Service

A summary and the status of the gaps already identified and described in D7.1 are described below.

- **GAP: Effective Accounting for PID Services:** To establish effective accounting of the PID Service in the EOSC ecosystem via the EOSC Accounting for Services, it is crucial to define the key metrics that should be collected. At present, there is no established method for obtaining quantitative data on the usage of PIDs across the EOSC ecosystem, which presents a significant gap in monitoring and reporting capabilities. Ongoing work is focused on identifying and describing the specific types of metrics that need to be exposed, with the goal of enabling comprehensive and meaningful accounting of PID-related activities.
- **GAP: Lack of machine-readable type descriptions, posing challenges in environments that rely on automated resource management and data interoperability:** In the EOSC ecosystem, various resources are available to support the research lifecycle and facilitate daily tasks. The integration of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) has enhanced this process, particularly for automating workflows within systems. However, despite PIDs being a key element for achieving interoperability, several challenges persist. Ongoing discussions are focused on initiating the processing of various resources utilized in the Marketplace and the Registry, to develop standardized type descriptions to support more consistent and efficient integration.
- **GAP: No service to assign and resolve PIDs:** A flexible PID service infrastructure, which is based on the Handle System, is used in order to support the data life cycle. This service is B2HANDLE, which provides a distributed service for storing, managing and accessing persistent identifiers and essential metadata (PID records). At present, the service is actively integrated with the Service Registry and the Marketplace, facilitating consistent referencing and metadata management. Additionally, ongoing developments aim to extend its use to the pilot nodes, further expanding its reach and functionality within the broader ecosystem.
- **GAP: Lack of a common interface to integrate with the PID service:** The PID service offers a well-documented API with functionalities that support the full lifecycle of data management, along with libraries to facilitate integration. The development is currently underway on an EOSC Core adapter, which will deliver the essential functionalities of the PID service. Additionally, ongoing collaboration with EOSC Services and pilot nodes is driving further integration efforts, ensuring the service aligns with user needs and technical requirements.

There are currently no updates or changes regarding the following identified GAPs.

- GAP: PID Service: support for custom PID namespaces

- GAP: Lack of a persistent identification system for scientific instruments for specific communities
- GAP: Check the Quality of Prefixes and PIDs used

4.11. Service Registry

Summary of gaps/requirements already identified and described in D7.1:

- **GAP: Service Catalogue needs to be offered as a deployable service** (ID: WP7-R131, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Deployable Service Catalogue: Finalisation of the Service Catalogue for EOSC Nodes (aaS, deployable service), ensuring local instances feature an off-the-shelf integration with EOSC AAI, EOSC PID service, and EOSC Messaging Service. Listing and linking to Resources in other EOSC Node instances highlighting the Resource Profile version used.)
- **GAP: Support of different service types** (ID: WP7-R130, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Support for Profile evolution: Specialisation of service types to include more specific properties (datasource, computing services, deployable services). Ability to adapt to resource profile changes)
- **GAP: PID support through the EOSC PID Service** (ID: WP7-R43, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Extending Integration Capabilities: Use of EOSC Messaging Service to integrate with EOSC Core components, support PIDs via EOSC PID service).
- **GAP: Service deduplication** (ID: WP7-R4, Requestor: DoA Service catalogue: support to service profile deduplication, enhanced integration with EOSC Core components, EOSC Execution Framework (EF), and EOSC Integration Suite (IS). Service Catalogue offered aaS/deployable.)
- **GAP: Integration with other EOSC Core components** (ID: WP7-R43, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Extending Integration Capabilities: Use of EOSC Messaging Service to integrate with EOSC Core components, support PIDs via EOSC PID service. Integration with other EOSC Core Components (Monitoring, Accounting, Helpdesk, etc.)
- **Use of a common communication channel across EOSC Core Components** (ID: WP7-R43, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Extending Integration Capabilities: Use of EOSC Messaging Service to integrate with EOSC Core components, support PIDs via EOSC PID service. Integration with other EOSC Core Components (Monitoring, Accounting, Helpdesk, etc.)
- **Support IF adapters and IG configuration templates** (ID: WP7-R132, Requestor: D5.1 TOSCA Deployable Services support: Include the ability for Providers to onboard a TOSCA-based deployable release of their services, compatible with the EOSC Deployment Service)

After post D7.1 analysis, **Support IF adapters and IG configuration templates** has been further extended by:

- Support for onboarding and curation of Adapters in the Service Registry: Service Registry will provide the API and necessary backend operations to support Adapters onboarding. Onboarding of adapters provided by Service Providers are to be automatically approved, while third-party Adapters will stay in pending state until a curation team (similar to EPOT) approves them.
- Support for Deployable Services as separate onboarding entities. The initial approach on Deployable Services was that Deployable Services are services that adhere to a special Interoperability Guideline, created for that purpose. Furthermore, the TOSCA template for a Deployable service was thought to be an IG configuration template for that special Guideline. The new approach is that Deployable Services are different from the standard services, and as such, they have their own Profile specification. Service Registry will fulfill this requirement which falls under WP7-R132 and WP7-R130 requirement descriptions.

For all new requirements, Tasks and Subtasks have been created in the Technical Roadmap Jira instance.

4.12. Providers' Dashboard

Summary of gaps already identified and described in D7.1:

- **GAP: Providers Dashboard adaptation to new profile specifications** (ID: WP7-R130, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Support for Profile evolution: Specialisation of service types to include more specific properties (datasource, computing services, deployable services). Ability to adapt to resource profile changes)
- **GAP: UI/UX redesign** (ID: WP7-R6 Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Service Providers Dashboard: redesigned UI/UX for uniform resource onboarding procedure across all different types of resources; UIs adaptable to resource profile changes)
- **GAP: Assistance tools for Providers** (ID: WP7-R51, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Assistance tools: Tools for Providers onboarding and advanced insights and analytics for their service portfolio across EOSC Nodes)

After post D7.1 analysis, **Providers Dashboard adaptation to new profile specifications** has been further extended by:

- Support for onboarding and curation of Adapters. This gap has already been described in the Service Registry section and will provide UI support for Adapter onboarding and curation operations as defined in the Adapter Onboarding process defined in WP11.

For this requirement, Tasks and Subtasks have been created in the Technical Roadmap Jira instance.

5. Conclusions

This final report articulates the results of a comprehensive process of gathering and analyzing requirements aimed at enhancing EOSC Core services within the EOSC Beyond project. The objective is to ensure that these services evolve in alignment with the dynamic needs of stakeholders, including end-users, service providers, and EOSC Nodes.

As the EOSC Innovation Sandbox progresses toward fostering a robust federation of national, regional, and thematic Nodes, the capabilities inherent to the EOSC Core must be designed for straightforward deployment or delivered as a service. The insights gathered from workshops and interactions with Pilot Nodes highlight the necessity of developing a more cohesively integrated EOSC Core platform, represented by the EOSC Innovation Sandbox, that effectively addresses user requirements. In more detail, this report integrates insights and decisions from two key workshops: the joint WP7 & WP8 Workshop held in Athens and the Pilot Nodes WP15 Workshop in Krakow.

During the WP7 & WP8 workshop in Athens a key gap was identified in the architecture of EOSC which is the lack of a dedicated service that enables the identification, search, listing, and querying of Nodes participating in the Federation, along with their respective federating capabilities.

This deliverable has identified more detailed gaps as a result of in-depth analyses of the integrations between Pilot Nodes, focusing on how they plan to enable composition among their respective resources within the Network of Pilot Nodes. Each identified gap has been translated into actionable requirements that will contribute to the ongoing requirements gathering and analysis process in EOSC Beyond. The requirements previously collected (as indicated in D7.1) have been systematically analyzed, broken down into actionable tasks and development tickets, and are currently undergoing the development process in Work Package 8 (WP8). This process will also apply to the new requirements that are accepted by the service teams.

The overarching goal is to cultivate an adaptive EOSC ecosystem that effectively meets the evolving demands of researchers, data providers, and EOSC Nodes, while further reinforcing the commitment to open science and enhancing collaboration across diverse research communities.

6. Acronyms

Term	Definition
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
aaS	as a Service
API	Application Programming Interface

Term	Definition
CIS	Core Innovation Sandbox
DCAT	Data Catalogue Vocabulary
DNS	Domain Name System
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
EF	Execution Framework (EOSC)
EMS	EOSC Messaging Service
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-A	European Open Science Cloud Association
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FDO	FAIR Digital Object
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
IF	Interoperability Framework
IS	Integration Suite
IG	Interoperability Guidelines
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
MFA	Multi Factor Authentication
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OpenID	Open standard and decentralised authentication protocol
PID	Persistent Identifier
SaaS	Service as a Service
SAML	Security Assertion Markup Language
SCIM	System for Cross-domain Identity Management
SIMPL	An open source, smart and secure middleware platform that supports data access and interoperability among European data spaces.
SSO	Single Sign On
TOSCA	Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications

Table 3: Acronyms

Appendix 1

Appendix 1 summarises the high-level requirements of EOSC Beyond's Pilot Nodes and identifies potential functional and technical gaps related to the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox.

Requirements and gaps recognised by the Pilot Nodes:

EGI Node

Requirements:

- Federated storage and computing services.
- Integration with AAI, order management and service catalogue.
- Resource orchestration and automated deployment.
- Monitoring and synchronisation with the EU Node.

Potential functional and technical gaps:

- Potential gaps in ensuring interoperability and composability between EGI's local services and the EOSC Core services, especially in the areas of resource allocation and monitoring.
- Challenges may arise in automating workflows for scaling resources across multiple Nodes.
- Limited user training and support for service tools.

CESSDA Node

Requirements:

- Seamless access to and tracking of resource usage.
- Reliable PID registration and resolution services.
- Single Sign-On access through federated AAI.

Potential functional and technical gaps:

- Integration between CESSDA's services and EOSC accounting and monitoring services might present challenges.
- Compatibility and management of AAI across institutions.
- Technical challenges in integrating PID services with existing infrastructure.

CNB-CSIC Node

Requirements:

- Cloud-based validation services for cryo-EM research.
- Federated data access and integration with cryo-EM repositories.
- Automated cloud deployment for periodic validation updates.
- Support for file transfer and resource allocation through the EOSC Execution Framework.

Potential functional and technical gaps:

- Resource limitations (e.g., GPUs, storage) for validation.
- Data management and compatibility between tools.

- Challenges in automating periodic updates to validation repositories.

Instruct ERIC Node

Requirements:

- Long-term storage solutions with accurate metadata management.
- Ability to provide proper public access with controlled data release.
- PID integration to track and link research outputs.

Potential functional and technical gaps:

- Reliable and transparent storage setups.
- Secure data management and release after embargo periods.
- Challenges in the accurate tracking of research outputs using PIDs.

e-INFRA CZ Node

Requirements:

- Integration of local AAI with EOSC AAI for cross-border collaboration.
- Secure data handling and sharing across Nodes.
- Scientific service registration and visibility in resource catalogues.
- Provision of a notebook service that allows data storage, analysis and sharing across Nodes.

Potential functional and technical gaps:

- Secure data transfer and sharing across Nodes.
- Complexity in synchronising data transfer services between national Nodes and EOSC services.
- Scalability challenges for supporting cross-Node execution of notebooks and workflows

ENES Node

Requirements:

- Federated AAI for secure access to computing resources.
- Cloud-based orchestration services for climate data analysis.
- Federated catalogues for data visibility and accessibility.

Potential functional and technical gaps:

- Resource limitations for big data processing and cloud computing.
- Integration challenges for data science tools with federated resources.
- Synchronisation of data collections across federated catalogues.

NFDI Node

Requirements:

- Federated AAI for flexible identity management.
- Secure access management for shared resources.
- Unique user identification across sessions.

Potential functional and technical gaps:

- Complexity in managing AAI across different institutions.
- Integration challenges with multiple identity providers.
- Difficulty in ensuring accurate user tracking for personalised services.

LifeWatch Node

Requirements:

- Federated metadata catalogues for ecosystem evaluation.
- High FAIR compliance and secure data backup for research activities.
- Integration of Virtual Research Environments (VREs).

Potential functional and technical gaps:

- Complexity in integrating catalogues with EOSC resources.
- Availability and retrieval of specific datasets.
- Consistent monitoring of FAIR principles for metadata.
- Challenges in managing ticketing and helpdesk support across multiple Nodes.

NI4OS Node

Requirements:

- Federated AAI for accessing research services.
- Cloud resources and thematic service catalogues.
- Integration with APIs for research simulations and climate data.

Potential functional and technical gaps:

- Complexity in integrating AAI and cloud resources.
- Harmonising thematic service APIs and cloud resources with EOSC standards.
- Challenges in federating access to climate research datasets.

METROFOOD Node

Requirements:

- Simplified single sign-on with federated AAI.
- Integration of METROFOOD catalogues with EOSC.
- Federated helpdesk services for user support.

Potential functional and technical gaps:

- Complexity in AAI integration for unified SSO.
- Ensuring FAIR data principles are fully met within METROFOOD’s catalogues.
- Integration issues with EOSC helpdesk services.

CORE SERVICES SUMMARY			
Service name	Requirements	Gaps/Problems to solve	Other remarks
Resource Discovery Hub	<p>Ability to federate and present multiple catalogues and datasets from national or thematic sources.</p> <p>Self-service access to services (e.g., booking instruments, running applications).</p> <p>Search functionality across federated nodes for both services and data assets.</p> <p>Capability to ingest feeds (e.g., OAI-PMH) and present harmonised views.</p>	<p>Lack of support for ingesting heterogeneous feeds with varying schemas.</p> <p>Missing connections between research products and discoverable services.</p> <p>Fragmentation in catalogue entries (thematic, institutional, or national silos). The lack of a unified, consistent, and cross-searchable presentation of services and resources in the Marketplace / Discovery Hub.</p> <p>Limited support for physical instruments (e.g., booking lab equipment) in the Discovery Hub.</p>	<p>The federation of domain-specific catalogues (e.g., CESSDA, METROFOOD) is repeatedly mentioned. There’s a strong user need to present curated, context-specific collections in the Resource Discovery Hub.</p>
Helpdesk	<p>Federated support infrastructure: local nodes should integrate their helpdesk into EOSC.</p> <p>Unified user support across services and platforms, regardless of backend provider.</p> <p>Thematic or organizational routing of support tickets (e.g., LifeWatch → EGI Helpdesk).</p>	<p>The EOSC Helpdesk is not yet uniformly integrated with national or domain-specific systems.</p> <p>No clear SLA monitoring or feedback loop is mentioned.</p> <p>Some pilots are unaware of how to connect their helpdesk workflows to EOSC’s.</p>	<p>Integration with existing ticketing systems is a recurring issue.</p> <p>The EOSC Helpdesk should support both technical and scientific queries.</p>

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Monitoring	Inclusion of service-specific probes for compute, storage, and data flows. Common guidelines for exposing status, reliability, and usage data. Monitoring must be able to ingest signals from HPC resources and federated services.	Missing documentation and integration paths for nodes to onboard monitoring tools. Lack of uniform visibility across federated environments. Some nodes are unaware of what metrics to collect or how to report them.	Several entries highlight the lack of probes or federation-wide monitoring schemes. EOSC-wide visibility is critical for resource planning, billing, and troubleshooting.
Service Catalogue	It should enable thematic filtering and the selection of exchange services. Needs to be usable as a backend to the Discovery Hub. Must support registration of internal and external services.	Currently, it lists all services without distinction (federated vs. local interest). No feature to let communities curate what is shown to their researchers. Connection to Helpdesk, Monitoring, and Order Management is not fully defined.	Nodes express the need for autonomy in controlling what appears in their Service Catalogue view.
AAI (Federated AAI Connector)	Federated identity access with role- or group-based permissions across infrastructures. Inclusion of community or national IdPs (e.g., ARIA, CEESDA).	The attribute harmonisation is unclear. Federation of group-based logic (e.g., cross-infrastructure group creation) is not supported.	
Deployment Service	Automated deployment of infrastructure services (compute, storage) from the catalogue. Support for binding deployments with research products or datasets.	No federation-aware orchestration of deployments across infrastructures. Resource allocation logic is still manual.	
PID Service	Assignment of persistent identifiers to stored datasets or published outputs. Ability to register and resolve PIDs seamlessly across EOSC tools.	PID workflows seem manual or disconnected from EOSC tools. No clarity on how storage or data repositories tie into PID registration.	

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Order Management	Interface to request services (e.g., compute, booking instruments) and track status. Federation-aware service ordering with feedback mechanisms.	Lack of SLA transparency or request tracking.	
Resource Catalogue	Register and federate institutional, national, and thematic resources. Enable nodes to curate what is visible within EOSC.	Some nodes have their own catalogues but cannot integrate or filter content appropriately. No clear schema compatibility or synchronisation process.	Repeated need for federation of metadata catalogues (CESSDA, METROFOOD, LifeWatch).

Table 4: Summary of the requirements and gaps identified by the Pilot Nodes per core service